

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Lived Experiences of BASC Students in the New Normal and its Implication for Instructional Effectiveness: A Grounded Theory Study

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Abstract

COVID-19 Pandemic has forced the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) to mandate Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines the paradigm shift of teaching-learning to distance learning called Flexible Learning Modality (FLM). Dealing with this, to determine the lived experiences of Bulacan Agricultural State College (BASC) students in the new normal and its implication for instructional effectiveness, this Grounded theory study aimed to describe the students' perception on the use of FLM, to determine the challenges and opportunities that students face in the new normal to determine ways to improve the teaching-learning process through the use of FLM. With the purposive sampling as the technique for acquiring the number of informants, and constructivist design of coding in generating assumptions, themes and core categories, a total of five emerging themes were extracted, namely (1) Work-study balance; (2) engaging, interactive and convenient; (3) less engaging, less effective and less interactive; (4) internet-related issues; and (5) leniency for sanity were the emerging themes extracted from the responses. The researchers developed a theoretical model from the responses of ten student-informants. The generated model describes the challenges and opportunities of students in the use of FLM that are influenced by the teacher factor, connectivity factor, and time factor. These challenges and opportunities led to several implications which will serve as grounds for the instructional effectiveness of FLM in tertiary education.

Keywords: Flexible Learning Modality, lived experiences, Grounded theory, Challenges and Opportunities, Instructional effectiveness

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1. Introduction

Year 2020 unprecedentedly led educators to distance education in the blink of an eye due to the threat of Coronavirus Disease (COVID) - 19 pandemic. As the World Health Organization (WHO) advised, the education sector must mitigate academic freeze and cancellations for the school year 2020-2021. Instead, different countries have been conducting several alternative learning methodologies and modalities to sustain the sphere of education and to continue to serve with quality education despite the health emergency crisis in line with the "New Normal" style of living.

Insubordinate to the advisory of WHO, in the Philippines, particularly in tertiary education, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) mandated the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to shift their paradigm in teaching-learning from Traditional way of teaching, also known as the Face-to-face Learning to distance learning called "Flexible Learning Modality."

Under the CHED Memorandum Order No. 4, s. 2020 contains the "Guidelines in the Implementation of Flexible Learning," this learning modality for HEIs is a pedagogical approach that allows flexibility on students' time, place, and audience but is not solely focused on the use of technology. Aside from, CMO No. 4 also identified that despite being in the use of technologies to gain education, its pedagogical features might vary on the levels of technology, availability of resources, internet connectivity, level of digital literacy, and approaches that are the main concerns of students who are in this kind of modality.

In Bulacan Agricultural State College, a local state college in Bulacan that did not experience this kind of modality since it was founded, the institution formulated the BASC- Flexible Learning Plan for the AY 2020-2021 that was approved by the BASC Board of Trustees under BOT Resolution 20-1309 on July 31, 2020. BASC-FLP mandates the approach of a